

Advancing the Measurement of Energy Justice: The EN-CAP Scale as a Capability Approach Instrument for Multidimensional Realities

Author names: Loos, Sabine^{ab}; Cellini, Marco^c; Striebing, Clemens^a; Fraudatario, Maria Camilla^c

^a Center for Responsible Research and Innovation, Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Engineering, Berlin, Germany

^b University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany

^c Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies, Italian National Research Council (IRPPS-CNR), Rome, Italy

Abstract

Assessing the societal implications of energy systems on a large scale remains a major conceptual and methodological challenge. Although existing measurement approaches, such as those focused on indicators like energy affordability or access, capture important aspects, they remain too narrow to capture the wider societal implications of energy systems, calling for a perspective that more fully reflects people's lived realities and needs. This study addresses this gap by developing and validating a survey instrument - the EN-CAP Scale - based on the Capability Approach (CA), translating Nussbaum's ten central capabilities into multidimensional energy capability measures to enable a comprehensive assessment of energy-related well-being. For this purpose, a large-scale online survey involving 30,000 respondents across Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa was conducted to evaluate the dimensionality and construct validity of the proposed measurement model. A structured, multi-step analytical procedure was employed, including an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), and Multi-Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis (MGCFA). The results support the overall validity and robustness of a six-factor model that comprehensively captures the societal implications of energy systems. This study contributes to advancing a theoretically grounded and empirically validated framework for large-scale measurement of energy-related well-being, providing a valuable tool for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners in pursuit of truly just and sustainable energy transitions.

1. Introduction

Energy systems shape societies through numerous mechanisms - including energy production, distribution infrastructure, or resource extraction - and inevitably create both winners and losers. The ongoing global energy transition, driven by the accelerated deployment of renewable energies as well as climate mitigation technologies, makes these dynamics increasingly visible. As new technologies and infrastructures enter communities, questions of public acceptance emerge (Devine-Wright, 2005; Ellis et al., 2023; Qazi et al., 2019; Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). At the same time, the transition intensifies existing justice concerns: the distribution of benefits and risks (distributive justice), the fairness of decision-making processes (procedural justice), and the recognition of diverse social groups and their lived realities (justice in recognition) (Heffron & McCauley, 2017; Jenkins et al., 2016; Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015). Beyond these, the transition raises broader and intersecting questions of power and inequality, including legacies of colonization, systemic sexism and racism, and the dispossession of Indigenous communities (Bell et al., 2020; Dunlap & Tornel, 2023; Gupta et al., 2023; Sovacool et al., 2023). Taken together, these dynamics highlight that the shift to a low-carbon energy system is not only a technological challenge but also a profoundly social and political one. As awareness of these justice-related issues deepens, understanding how to design truly just and inclusive energy systems has become a crucial research and policy concern.

To date, the societal implications of energy systems have been studied in two main ways. Some research has focused on qualitative, in-depth case studies, providing rich but localized insights (Cantoni et al., 2022; Middlemiss & Gillard, 2015; Moniruzzaman & Day, 2020; Sovacool et al., 2019). Other approaches have employed quantitative indicators, such as the energy burden, to assess energy impacts on a broader scale, albeit in a more limited, often economically-centered way. However, societal impacts are complex and multidimensional, and existing quantitative indicators fail to capture their full scope (Baker et al., 2023; David & Kod'ousková, 2023; Herrero, 2017), highlighting the need for approaches that better reflect people's lived experiences and needs. At the same time, measuring these impacts on a large scale remains methodologically challenging, requiring indicators that are both comprehensive and comparable across regions. In response to this gap, the Capability Approach (CA) developed by Nussbaum (2000a, 2000b) offers a promising framework for assessing well-being and multidimensional capabilities in relation to energy systems. By shifting the focus from narrow economic measures to the actual freedoms and opportunities people enjoy to live the lives they truly value, this approach can capture a broader spectrum of societal impacts. Yet, to the best of our knowledge, there are no existing large-scale quantitative studies that have operationalized the CA specifically in the energy context and provided cross-regional validation.

The primary aim of this study is to develop and validate a survey instrument to measure the societal implications of energy systems from a capability perspective. Specifically, we address the following research questions: Can the CA be reliably operationalized in a large international sample to assess the impacts of energy systems on well-being? Which dimensions of societal impacts are captured by this operationalization? Is the resulting scale invariant across regions?

This study makes several contributions. Theoretically, it applies and extends the CA to the context of energy systems. Methodologically, it operationalizes the approach through a large-scale quantitative survey and validates the resulting measurement instrument, the Energy-Capabilities Scale (EN-CAP Scale). Practically, it provides a tool for policymakers and researchers, to assess the societal implications of energy systems comprehensively, supporting the design of just and sustainable energy transitions.

To contextualize these contributions, the study first positions itself within the broader literature on societal dimensions of energy systems. The theoretical background is organized in two parts: first, it reviews existing approaches to assessing the societal dimensions of energy systems; second, it shows how these frameworks can be extended through a capability-based perspective to capture more fully how energy systems shape opportunities and freedoms. The paper then presents the methodology, followed by the survey-based findings and the validated measurement instrument, and discusses the theoretical, methodological, and practical implications of this instrument for advancing just and sustainable energy transitions. Finally, the study closes with a concise conclusion summarizing the main contributions, reflecting on limitations, and outlining avenues for future research.

2. Theoretical Background: Measuring Societal Impacts of Energy Dimensions

Existing Approaches to Assessing the Societal Dimensions of Energy Systems

Energy plays a fundamental and multifaceted role as an enabler of basic human needs and the broader pursuit of human development, serving not merely as an end in itself but as a vital condition for individual well-being. Access to adequate energy services - such as heating, cooling, lighting, cooking, and mobility - underpins essential dimensions of well-being, including health, education, and social participation (Baltruszewicz et al., 2023; Brand-Correa & Steinberger, 2017; Day et al., 2016; Hillerbrand & Goldammer, 2018; Liao et al., 2021; Rao & Wilson, 2022; Thomson et al., 2017a, 2017b). The study of energy's role in human well-being inevitably highlights its deep entanglement with issues of social justice. Not all individuals experience the impacts of energy systems equally, whether in terms of affordability and access to safe, clean, and reliable energy sources (Bouzarovski, 2014; European Commission, 2022a, 2022b; Thomson et al., 2017b) or in terms of the ways energy services expand opportunities and capabilities in everyday life, supporting activities such as leisure, work, or study (Bartiaux et al., 2018; Day et al., 2016; Velasco-Herrejon et al., 2020). These unequal experiences reflect broader patterns of social and structural disadvantage, shaped by factors rooted in historical legacies and systemic discrimination, which influence who benefits from and who is burdened by energy systems (Sovacool et al., 2023; 2025).

Such inequalities are evident both globally - between countries in the Global North and the Global South, where some populations enjoy energy abundance while others face chronic shortages - and within countries, where structural inequalities mean that some individuals live in energy excess while others cannot meet even their basic energy needs (Galvin & Sunikka-Blank, 2018; Gore, 2020; Wiedmann et al., 2020). Against this background, research at the

intersection of energy and justice has expanded rapidly in recent years. Theoretical concepts such as energy justice, energy poverty, fuel poverty, energy equity, energy democracy, and energy vulnerability have increasingly guided both empirical studies and theoretical debates (Baker et al., 2023; Ferrall-Wolf et al., 2023; Hall et al., 2013; Hihetah et al., 2024; Jenkins et al., 2016, 2021; Ren et al., 2025; Sy & Mokaddem, 2022). Literature around these concepts illustrates that energy systems do not affect all individuals equally but rather have differential impacts across social groups. Scholars highlight how disparities in energy access and service provision can reinforce existing social inequalities, leaving some populations disproportionately vulnerable. According to the energy justice framework, typically operationalized through its three core tenets - distributional justice, procedural justice, and justice in recognition - inequities in the energy sector manifest across multiple dimensions, encompassing not only the unequal distribution of energy resources but also disparities in decision-making processes and the recognition of diverse social groups (Jenkins et al., 2016; Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015).

Identifying and quantifying exposure to energy injustices on a large scale is commonly undertaken through the measurement of energy poverty - defined as “the inability to attain a socially and materially necessitated level of domestic energy services” (Bouzarovski & Petrova, 2015). This approach offers a tangible framework for evaluating key dimensions such as energy access, affordability, and efficiency (Bouzarovski & Petrova, 2015). The corresponding indicators predominantly address objective socio-economic aspects of deprivation, such as the energy burden, typically defined as the percentage of household income spent on meeting energy needs (Bouzarovski, 2014). Yet, while the energy burden metric offers a straightforward means of identifying households facing disproportionate energy costs relative to their income and enables comparability across contexts, it has been widely criticized for relying on arbitrary thresholds, ignoring household needs and housing costs, neglecting the depth of deprivation, and often lacking representativeness (Baker et al., 2023; Herrero, 2017) and for capturing only a narrow, economic dimension of energy vulnerability, overlooking broader experiential and structural aspects (Baker et al., 2023; David & Kod’ousková, 2023). For instance, expenditure-based measures of energy poverty frequently fail to take into account the specific housing arrangements and overall living conditions of households, such as the presence of energy-efficient appliances, or the household composition, all of which can have a significant impact on actual energy consumption and thus distort assessments of energy poverty (Menyhért, 2024). In a similar vein, Snell et al. (2015) highlight the limitations of applying uniform assumptions to household energy requirements, noting that people with certain disabilities or medical conditions often face higher energy demands (see also Thomson et al., 2017b) suggesting that conventional measures such as the energy burden fail to fully capture these nuanced forms of energy injustice.

From Existing Frameworks to a Capability-Based Understanding of Energy’s Societal Impacts

In response to the mounting recognition that socio-economic measures of energy justice often provide only a partial view of inequality and inequity, there is an increasing demand for more comprehensive and integrated approaches. Responding to this, in recent years, there has been

growing scholarly attention to the relationship between energy and broader dimensions of human well-being (Guevara et al., 2023). Baltruszewicz et al. (2023), for example, stress the importance of viewing energy not merely as a technical input but as a socially embedded resource that shapes opportunities for human flourishing. To better understand these dynamics, conceptual frameworks have been developed to articulate how energy translates into services that contribute to human well-being, highlighting the intermediate steps through which energy enables basic needs, opportunities, and ultimately well-being outcomes (Day et al., 2016; Kalt et al., 2019).

The CA pioneered by Amartya Sen and further advanced by Martha Nussbaum, has in recent years emerged as a leading framework for examining well-being within the social sciences. In addressing the question “equality of what?”, Sen (1992, p. xi) argues that true equality lies in “our capability to achieve valuable functionings that make up our lives, and more generally, our freedom to promote objectives we have reason to value.” This perspective reframes development away from economic indicators toward the substantive freedoms and opportunities people have to live the lives they value (Sen, 1999, 2014). Building upon Sen’s foundational work, Nussbaum (2000a, 2000b) developed the CA into a more explicitly normative framework by introducing a list of central universal capabilities, encompassing aspects such as health, bodily integrity, emotions, social affiliation (see Table 1 for an overview of all ten capabilities). These serve as political principles specifying the fundamental opportunities and conditions required for a life worthy of human dignity and well-being. Nussbaum (2003) contends that, rather than using outcomes or resources as proxies for justice, the CA - by focusing on what individuals are genuinely able to do and be - provides a deeper insight into the structural and contextual obstacles that hinder the realization of true justice and well-being.

With its broad and integrative perspective, the CA has gained increasing prominence in the study of energy justice, offering a framework that extends beyond the assessment of material access or affordability (Melin et al., 2021). For example, Velasco-Herrejon and Bauwens (2020) examine community acceptance of wind energy among marginalized indigenous populations in Mexico. They reveal how wind farms affect citizens’ central capabilities and how these in turn influence the acceptance of wind technologies. Bartiaux et al. (2021) use Nussbaum’s framework to show how energy-poor households in Belgium experience deprivations across multiple capabilities that reinforce each other in vicious circles. Extending the CA to the realm of policy evaluation, Willand et al. (2021) examine energy vulnerability policies and initiatives in Victoria, Australia. Focusing on bodily health, they argue that unequal access to adequate heating stems from structural, geographical, and cultural conditions, not merely income, and call for interdisciplinary, multi-level policy approaches. Taking yet another angle, Hillerbrand et al. (2021) argue that the CA offers valuable normative guidance for assessing technological developments in the energy sector with regard to ethical and social challenges. Building on the earlier work of Hillerbrand and Goldammer (2018) - who identified key aspects of energy systems that shape human well-being and linked them to Nussbaum’s central capabilities – the authors demonstrate, through case studies on smart grids and autonomous vehicles, how the CA provides a structured framework for the normative evaluation of truly responsible and sustainable technological change.

When energy justice is examined through the lens of the CA, this is most often done using qualitative methods within case study frameworks. This reflects the broader application of the CA, which has traditionally been employed for context-sensitive, qualitative analyses of individual and collective well-being (Bartolomei et al., 2024). Attempts to operationalize this approach quantitatively remain rare. So far, only one study by Bartiaux et al. (2018) has developed a conceptual and quantifiable framework for applying the CA to energy justice, which was tested in Belgium. To our knowledge, similar approaches of this kind have not been developed and have so far been explored primarily in sectors outside the energy domain. For instance, Cao and Hickman (2019, 2020) applied the CA to the transport sector in Beijing, examining how individual characteristics, mobility options, and the urban environment shape people's capabilities. Similarly, Azmoodeh et al. (2023) used a survey-based quantitative approach to assess how personal and contextual factors influence residents' transport-related capabilities in Tehran. In the field of public health, Lorgelly et al. (2015) developed the OCAP-18 measurement instrument to operationalize the CA for evaluating the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of public health interventions.

Translating the CA into quantitative frameworks holds significant potential for capturing the multidimensional aspects of the energy system's influence on human well-being, particularly through large-scale, cross-country comparative analyses. Building on this potential, our study aims to develop and validate an instrument which comprehensively measures the societal impacts of the energy system through the lens of the CA. To this end, we developed a detailed quantitative survey framework grounded in the CA, which was implemented in a large-scale, cross-national survey to investigate individuals' energy-related capabilities. Using the resulting survey data, we applied a combination of factor analysis techniques to validate the scales and assess their reliability and suitability for future research applications. This approach allows for a rigorous, multidimensional evaluation of how energy systems enable - or constrain - people's well-being across diverse national contexts.

3. Method: Developing an Instrument to Capture Energy Capabilities

3.1 Survey Instrument Development

Building upon the CA as articulated by Nussbaum (2000a, 2000b) and her specification of the ten central capabilities, a conceptual framework to measure the societal impacts of energy systems was developed. The objective was to operationalize energy-related capabilities - hereafter referred to as energy capabilities - to capture how energy systems affect human well-being and justice dimensions.

To inform the framework, we conducted an extensive literature review, focusing on recent empirical and theoretical studies that apply the CA in energy and mobility contexts (e.g., Bartiaux et al., 2018; Cao & Hickman, 2019, 2020; Day et al., 2016, 2023; Hickman et al., 2017; Hillerbrand & Goldammer, 2018; Hillerbrand et al., 2021; Velasco-Herrejon & Bauwens, 2020). Building on these insights, we operationalized the framework as a 26-item questionnaire,

with multiple items developed for each of Nussbaum’s ten core capabilities to ensure a comprehensive representation of the ways energy systems affect daily life and overall well-being. The questionnaire was developed collaboratively by a team of three researchers at Fraunhofer IAO through a fully iterative process. Initial proposals for energy capabilities were based on Nussbaum’s (2000a, 2000b) ten central capabilities and further informed by the energy-specific conceptualizations of Hillerbrand and Goldammer (2018) and Bartiaux et al. (2018), as well as the unpublished questionnaire by Day et al. (2023). Items were critically reviewed, refined, rephrased, or removed during structured sessions to ensure clarity, consistency, and relevance. This iterative process yielded a robust set of energy capabilities that reflect normative criteria for assessing the societal impacts of energy systems. Table 1 summarizes the outcome, showing how Nussbaum’s ten capabilities were adapted to the energy context and the corresponding 26 questionnaire items.¹

Table 1: Translating Nussbaum’s Ten Central Capabilities into the Energy Context

Capability	Indicator	Label
1 Life: Being able to live a full human lifespan and not die prematurely.	Are you able to avoid exposure to harmful pollution (concerning air, noise, water, soil etc.)?	C1_Pollution
2 Bodily Health: Being able to be healthy, well-nourished, and have adequate shelter.	Is your health impacted by affordability or availability of your energy use?	C2_Health
	Is your health impacted by the energy situation in your area?	C2_LocalEnergyEffects
3 Bodily Integrity: Being able to move freely and be safe from violence	Are you able to move from one place to another without fear of energy-related hazards?	C3_SafeMobility
4 Senses, Imagination & Thought: Being able to use one’s mind and senses, to think, reason, imagine, and enjoy education, art, religion, and pleasurable experiences, with freedom of expression.	Are you able to make informed decisions about your energy use?	C4_InformedDecision
	Are you able to form an opinion about energy issues such as energy sources available and how energy is produced or distributed?	C4_EnergyOpinion
	Are you able to make conscious choices about your energy use in line with your values?	C4_ConsciousEnergyUse
5 Emotions: Being able to form attachments, love, grieve, and experience emotions without fear or anxiety.	Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to study or work at home?	C5_StudyWork
	Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to have visitors to your home?	C5_Hosting
	Does affordability or availability of energy impact your sense of safety and security in your home?	C5_HomeSecurity
6 Practical Reason: Being able to reflect on and plan one’s life according to one’s values, with freedom of conscience.	Are you able to optimize and manage your energy consumption in the most efficient way possible?	C6_EnergyManagement
	Do you feel competent about energy policies and regulations that may impact your energy choices?	C6_PolicyCompetence
	Are you able to avoid unnecessary waste of energy in your household?	C6_WasteAvoidance

¹ Further, Table 1 in Annex 1 (Analysis Complete Report) expands on this by presenting the full initial item set, including descriptive labels and the R coding structure. In Annex 1, all items appear in their original format, identified by the automatically generated Q-codes that were also used for the R computations. For the manuscript, however, we renamed all items and assigned each one a unique, intuitive label. Throughout the paper, we refer only to these revised labels.

7 Affiliation: i) Being able to live with others, show concern, compassion, and form friendships and just relationships; ii) Being able to have self-respect, dignity, and be free from discrimination.	<i>To what extent do the following experiences apply to your overall household energy use for cooking, heating, lighting, and electricity?</i> I can afford the amount of energy and energy resources needed to supply all areas of my household. Energy and energy resources are available to me in the needed amount to supply my household. My households' energy and energy resources supply is reliable without outages. My households' energy use including material sourcing and generating energy causes no damage or risk for my health.	C7_Affordability C7_Availability C7_Reliability C7_Safety
8 Other Species: Being able to live in relation to and care for animals, plants, and nature.	Are you able to engage in environmental and climate protection? Are you able to choose to use renewable energy sources (for cooking, heating, vehicle's fuel, etc.)? Are you able to choose environmentally friendly alternatives when you make purchasing decisions?	C8_EcoAction C8_Renewables C8_EcoPurchasing
9 Play: Being able to laugh, play, and enjoy recreational activities.	Do you have access to unspoiled and uncontaminated natural landscape close to your home? Can you access transportation without any restriction to move from one place to another? Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to access online and digital communication services such as websites, messaging, and phone calls? Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to enjoy recreational activities (such as TV, radio, and music) and hobbies in your home?	C9_NatureAccess C9_TransportAccess C9_DigitalAccess C9_Recreation
10 Control Over One's Environment ² : i) Being able to participate effectively in political life and exercise free speech and association; ii) Being able to own property, seek employment freely, and work meaningfully with others.	<i>Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with each of the statements.</i> Politicians strive to keep in close touch with the people regarding energy issues. Politicians care about what ordinary people think about energy issues.	C10_PoliticiansContact C10_PoliticiansCare

Source: Authors' elaboration drawing on Nussbaum's (2000a, 2000b) capability definitions

3.2 Data Collection

Building on the operationalization of the energy capabilities questionnaire, the next step involved collecting empirical data to examine how these capabilities manifest across diverse societal contexts. To this end, a large-scale, cross-national survey was conducted as part of the gEneSys project, which aims to examine intersectional patterns in societal impacts of the energy system. The survey was administered by the research institute Fraunhofer IAO in collaboration with gEneSys project partners as well as the international market research agency Ipsos. Data

² For certain items, validated scales were adapted. The items used for Control over one's environment were adapted from the Political Efficacy Short Scale (PESS) developed by Groskurth et al. (2021) to fit the energy context.

collection occurred between October 14, 2024, and January 21, 2025, across ten countries - six in the European Union (France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Sweden) and four in Sub-Saharan Africa (Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, Uganda), yielding a final sample of 30,001 respondents. To ensure that the energy capabilities could be consistently measured across these diverse contexts, the original questionnaire was developed in English and then professionally translated into all relevant national and regional languages (e.g., Swahili and Luganda for Uganda; French, German, Polish, Portuguese, Swedish), in close collaboration with gEneSys project partners and Ipsos.

Survey participants were selected using quota-based sampling from the Ipsos online panel infrastructure, with quotas set for age, gender, region (typically NUTS 2 or NUTS 1), and education level in all countries except Kenya, Nigeria, and Uganda, where only age and gender were considered due to regional constraints. The survey targeted adult residents with internet access, aged 18–75 in the European countries and 18–65 in the Sub-Saharan countries. These design choices allowed for broad coverage while acknowledging regional data collection limitations. Surveys were administered online using Ipsos’ proprietary panels. Participants were invited via email, and incentives followed a standardised point-based system common in commercial online research to avoid biasing participation across demographic groups. Respondent verification was performed using double opt-in, geolocation, CAPTCHA codes, and real-time algorithms to monitor speeding and straight-lining behaviour. Data quality control included automatic removal of inattentive responses and enforcement of participation limits to prevent oversampling of frequent panellists.

3.3 Analytical Strategy

Once the data from the multinational survey were collected, the latent structure of the 26-item energy capability scale was examined. The analysis consists of a structured multi-step approach, including data preparation and preprocessing, treatment of missing data, assessment of factorability, and evaluation of multicollinearity and normality assumptions. Subsequently, Exploratory Factor Analysis (henceforth EFA) (Fabrigar & Wegener, 2012), Confirmatory Factor Analysis (henceforth CFA) (Harrington, 2009), and Multi Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis (MG-CFA) (Farmer & Lawrence Farmer, 2014) were conducted to empirically test the latent structure and assess the scale’s construct validity. The analyses were conducted in R, employing packages within the tidyverse, psychometrics, and structural equation modelling ecosystems.

The following subsections detail each analytical phase and the statistical procedures implemented. To complement the methodological section reported here, a comprehensive description of the methodological strategy and the results is provided in Appendix 1 – Analysis Complete Report.

Data Preparation and Preprocessing

The initial item pool consisted of 26 questions designed to assess energy-related impacts on human well-being. Responses were recorded on a seven-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = “Do not agree at all” to 7 = “Completely agree.” An exception was made for the items related

to Control Over One's Environment (C10_PoliticiansContact and C10_PoliticiansCare), which were measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 = "Do not agree at all" to 5 = "Completely agree." Items reflected diverse conceptual domains including energy access, affordability, self-efficacy, and institutional trust. Seven items (e.g., C2_Health, C2_LocalEnergyEffects) were negatively worded and reverse-coded during preprocessing to ensure directional consistency. To harmonize distributions across scales and facilitate model convergence in subsequent analyses, all items were subsequently standardized (z-scores). Additionally, a derived categorical variable (REGION) was created to compare measurement invariance across contexts, with respondents from European countries coded as "Global North" and those from African countries as "Global South".

Missing Data Strategy

Item-level missingness ranged from 0.5% to 9.6%, with negatively worded items (e.g., C2_Health, C2_LocalEnergyEffects) showing higher nonresponse. To assess the nature of missingness patterns within the data we employed the Little's Missing Completely at Random test (Little's MCAR), which strongly rejected the null hypothesis of data being MCAR ($p < .001$), indicating that missingness followed either Missing at Random (MAR) or Missing not at Random (MNAR) mechanisms. Once assessed, missing data were not completely at random, to mitigate potential biases from listwise deletion and reduce uncertainty (Rubin, 1987; Schafer & Graham, 2002), a multiple imputation strategy was adopted (see Annex 1 - Analysis Complete Report for complete documentation). To make sure data imputation did not affect the overall data structure, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by comparing regression models on both imputed and unimputed datasets (see Annex 1 - Analysis Complete Report). Results across models were consistent in direction, magnitude, and significance of coefficients, justifying the use of imputation.

Assessment of Factorability

Prior to performing the EFA, we examined the data's suitability for factor analyses through two diagnostic tests: Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy (MSA). Bartlett's test yielded a highly significant result ($\chi^2 = 298,740.3$, $df = 325$, $p < 0.001$), indicating non-zero correlations among items. The KMO value was 0.90, considered excellent, with all item-level MSAs exceeding the 0.60 threshold (Kaiser, 1974). Together, these diagnostics confirmed that the data were appropriate for factor analysis (see Annex 1 - Analysis Complete Report for full documentation).

Multicollinearity and Normality Checks

To ensure the appropriateness of the factor model, we tested multicollinearity among the items. Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) were computed for all scale items (see Annex 1 - Analysis Complete Report) and found to range between 1.15 and 2.4, well below conventional thresholds (5.0 or 2.5), indicating acceptable multicollinearity levels. Pairwise correlations did not exceed 0.8, confirming that no multicollinearity adjustments were required.

The distribution of each item was also examined to check whether normality assumption was met, and most items showed a moderate deviation from perfect normality, being slightly skewed

to the left and more peaked than expected. Formal tests of normality such as skewness and kurtosis statistics, as well as Anderson-Darling tests confirmed that these deviations were statistically significant. At the multivariate level, Mardia's test also indicated that the joint distribution of the items was not normal. Since violation of normality can bias standard errors and model fit statistics when using standard maximum likelihood estimation, the confirmatory factor model was estimated with the Maximum Likelihood with Robust standard errors estimator (MLR), which is a robust version of maximum likelihood providing corrected standard errors and fit indices then the data do not meet normality assumptions.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA): Exploring the Underlying Structure of the Items

Having confirmed that multicollinearity was within acceptable limits and accounting for deviations from normality through the use of robust estimation, we proceeded to explore the underlying structure of the items. An EFA was conducted using Principal Axis Factoring (Horn, 1965) with oblimin rotation to accommodate correlated latent dimensions. Parallel Analysis recommended the retention of six factors. The six-factor solution explained 43.2% of total variance, which is considered acceptable in social science contexts involving complex human capabilities. In terms of factor retention, we prioritized parallel analysis over the eigenvalue-greater-than-one rule and scree plot visual inspection, as the latter are more prone to subjectivity and overestimation (Zwick & Velicer, 1986). The use of oblique rotation was also theoretically driven, as dimensions of energy-related capabilities are expected to be interdependent rather than orthogonal.

A cutoff value of 0.30 has been applied, and items scoring lower values have not been retained. Table 2 reports a summary of the standardized loadings for each item on the retained factors.

Table 22: EFA loadings by factor (cutoff = .30)

Item	MR1	MR2	MR3	MR4	MR5	MR6
C2 Health		0.713				
C2 LocalEnergyEffects		0.685				
C3 SafeMobility				0.367		
C4 InformedDecision					0.774	
C4 EnergyOpinion					0.496	
C5 StudyWork		0.601				
C5 Hosting		0.440				0.395
C5 HomeSecurity		0.513				
C4 ConsciousEnergyUse					0.618	
C6 EnergyManagement	0.523					
C6 PolicyCompetence	0.428					
C6 WaseAvoidance	0.452					
C8 EcoAction	0.649					
C8 Renewables	0.651					
C8 EcoPurchasing	0.695					
C9 DigitalAccess		0.782				
C9 Recreation		0.794				
C7 Affordability				0.639		
C7 Availability				0.801		
C7 Reliability				0.742		
C7 Safety				0.541		
C10 PoliticiansContact			0.858			
C10 PoliticiansCare			0.873			

Source: authors' elaboration

Three items (C1_Pollution, C5_StudyWork, C9_TransportAccess) failed to load significantly on any factor and were flagged for possible exclusion in subsequent CFA. Factors were interpreted based on the pattern of item loadings, yielding six domains consistent with theoretical expectations. The decision to use EFA before CFA aligns with best practices in scale development and cross-cultural research (DeVellis & Thorpe, 2021).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): Confirming the Factor Structure with a More Rigid Test

Based on the EFA results, a CFA model was specified, excluding C1_Pollution, C5_StudyWork and C9_TransportAccess, and retaining six latent factors. Each factor was defined by 2 to 6 indicators, and two residual covariances (C6_EnergyManagement $\sim\sim$ C6_WasteAvoidance; C9_DigitalAccess $\sim\sim$ C9_Recreation) were added based on strong modification indices. The model was estimated using the robust MLR estimator. Internal consistency was evaluated using both Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω for each factor. All six dimensions demonstrated good reliability ($\alpha \geq .73$, $\omega \geq .74$), with particularly strong performance for Factors 2 and 6 ($\alpha/\omega > .85$). These values indicate acceptable internal cohesion for each latent construct.

Multi-Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis (MGCFA): Checking Whether the Scale Works the Same Across Regions

Eventually, to examine the cross-regional validity of the energy capability scale, we implemented a Multi-Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis (MGCFA) comparing responses from the Global North and Global South. This step was crucial to test whether the scale measures the same constructs equivalently across culturally and socioeconomically diverse populations. We followed the standard invariance testing procedure (Brown, 2006; Milfont & Fischer, 2010), fitting a hierarchy of nested models: Configural Invariance, Metric Invariance, Scalar Invariance, and Partial Scalar Invariance. All models were evaluated using CFI, RMSEA, and SRMR, complemented by χ^2 difference testing. The use of partial invariance (Byrne et al., 1989) is widely considered acceptable for cross-group comparisons of latent means and was deemed necessary given the minor differences across regions. The robustness of the partial invariance solution was supported by theoretical considerations and empirical fit improvements.

4. Findings

Following data preparation and standardization, and after confirming the data factorability, absence of multicollinearity, presence of non-normality, and that the use of imputed data was justified by the sensitivity analysis, the EFA results suggested a six-factor structure. To strengthen the validity of the scale, we followed the standard three-step sequence used in psychometric research: 1) EFA, 2) CFA, 3) MGCFA. EFA is used first because it allows the underlying factor structure to emerge directly from the data without imposing strong a priori constraints; this is essential when working with a newly developed instrument or when the theoretical structure needs empirical verification. Once the preliminary structure is identified, CFA is then applied to formally test how well this factor model fits the data, using a more

rigorous framework that specifies which items load on which latent dimensions and evaluates overall model fit. Finally, MGCFA extends this assessment by testing whether the scale operates equivalently across different groups (in our case, across countries from the Global North and Global South). This step is crucial for establishing measurement invariance, ensuring that the latent constructs are measured in the same way across the different groups.

4.1 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The initial CFA model was specified using the six-factor solution derived from EFA, excluding C1_Pollution, C5_StudyWork, C9_TransportAccess. Fit indices for the initial model (Table 3) indicated a reasonable fit.

The internal consistency of the model has been assessed through Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω (reported in Table 3), which demonstrates robust internal consistency across its dimensions.

Table 33: Factors' Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω

Factor	Items	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
Factor 1	C6_EnergyManagement, C6_PolicyCompetence, C6_WasteAvoidance, C8_EcoAction, C8_Renewables, C8_EcoPurchasing	0.808	0.809
Factor 2	C5_StudyWork, C5_Hosting, C5_HomeSecurity, C9_DigitalAccess, C9_Recreation	0.862	0.863
Factor 3	C7_Affordability, C7_Availability, C7_Reliability, C7_Safety, C3_SafeMobility	0.792	0.797
Factor 4	C2_Health, C2_LocalEnergyEffects	0.803	0.803
Factor 5	C4_InformedDecision, C4_EnergyOpinion, C4_ConsciousEnergyUse	0.733	0.739
Factor 6	C10_PoliticiansContact, C10_PoliticiansCare	0.854	0.854

Source: authors' elaboration

The analysis of the Modification Indices (MI), however, highlighted room for model improvement. In particular, the exceptionally high modification index (MI = 4921) between C9_DigitalAccess and C9_Recreation indicates a strong residual correlation, likely due to shared item content or wording. Both items load on the same factor, as do C6_EnergyManagement and C6_WasteAvoidance (MI = 1985.), which also show a substantial residual correlation. These patterns supported the inclusion of residual covariances for these item pairs. Other high MIs suggest that items such as C5_Hosting, C8_Renewables, C9_DigitalAccess, and C9_Recreation may also load on additional factors, potentially reflecting conceptual overlap. However, including numerous cross-loadings would increase the risk of overfitting and weaken the distinctiveness of the latent constructs. For this reason, we chose to include only the cross-loadings that were theoretically most defensible.

We therefore re-run a second CFA model, adding two residual correlations: C6_EnergyManagement $\sim\sim$ C6_WasteAvoidance and C9_DigitalAccess $\sim\sim$ C9_Recreation. The revised model showed improved fit. Table 4 reports the fit indices for both the initial and the final models.

Table 44: Fit indices for the final CFA model

Fit Index	Initial CFA Model Value	Final CFA Model Value
χ^2 (df = 213)	15,098.174	10424.62
CFI	0.927	0.950
TLI	0.914	0.941
RMSEA	0.056 (90% CI: 0.055–0.057)	0.047 (90% CI: 0.046–0.047)
SRMR	0.045	0.043
AIC	1,700,363.19	1,693,956.28
BIC	1,700,870.033	1,694,479.75

Source: authors' elaboration

These values indicate a good fit according to Hu and Bentler's criteria (1999), particularly considering the model's complexity and non-normality of data (for which MLR was used). Table 5 reports on the individual factor loadings for all items.

Table 55: Final CFA items' standardized Loadings

Factor	Item	Standard Loading
Factor1	C6 EnergyManagement	0.659
	C6 PolicyCompetence	0.588
	C6 WaseAvoidance	0.552
	C8 EcoAction	0.671
	C8 Renewables	0.625
	C8 EcoPurchasing	0.721
Factor2	C5 StudyWork	0.790
	C5 Hosting	0.748
	C5 HomeSecurity	0.701
	C9 DigitalAccess	0.709
	C9 Recreation	0.700
Factor3	C7 Affordability	0.678
	C7 Availability	0.798
	C7 Reliability	0.706
	C7 Safety	0.623
	C3 SafeMobility	0.505
Factor4	C2 Health	0.844
	C2 LocalEnergyEffects	0.795
Factor5	C4 InformedDecision	0.749
	C4 EnergyOpinion	0.597
	C4 ConsciousEnergyUse	0.740
Factor6	C10 PoliticiansContact	0.909
	C10 PoliticiansCare	0.819

Source: authors' elaboration

All items showed strong standardized loadings (> .60) except C3_SafeMobility (.478), C6_PolicyCompetence (.588) and C6_WaseAvoidance (.552). Although these three items load slightly below the conventional .60 threshold, their coefficients remain within an acceptable range for applied CFA, as values above .40 are generally considered adequate indicators of a latent construct (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007), particularly when the overall model fit is strong and the items carry clear theoretical relevance. Therefore, we retained them in the final model. Moreover, the six latent constructs remained well-differentiated with moderate inter-factor correlations. Overall, the final CFA model shows excellent fit, with all fit indices reaching or exceeding standard thresholds.

The modification indices for the final CFA model indicate residual sources of localized misfit, notably involving item C8_Renewables, which exhibits several high cross-loadings. While these indices suggest potential improvements to model fit, no additional modifications were implemented at this stage in order to preserve the parsimony and theoretical clarity of the model.

4.2 Multi Group Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Lastly, measurement invariance analysis was conducted through MGCFA to assess whether the latent capability constructs related to energy are equivalently measured across two major global regions: the Global North and the Global South. The process followed the standard sequence: configural, metric, and scalar models.

To do so, we began by estimating the configural model because this is the first and least restrictive step in measurement invariance testing. The configural model evaluates whether the basic factor structure (i.e., the number of factors and the pattern of item–factor relationships) is consistent across groups without imposing equality constraints on the parameters. Establishing configural invariance is essential because it provides the baseline against which more restrictive models (metric and scalar invariance) are compared. If groups do not share the same underlying factor structure, then comparisons of factor loadings or intercepts would not be meaningful. Once configural invariance was supported, we proceeded to test metric and scalar invariance by sequentially adding equality constraints and examining changes in model fit.

Configural model: Confirming the Basic Factor Structure Across Regions

The configural model demonstrates excellent fit: $\chi^2 = 14,604.79$; CFI = 0.948; TLI = 0.938; RMSEA = 0.047; and SRMR = 0.043. The model indicates that the underlying factor structure is consistent across both regions. This implies that respondents from the Global North and South interpret the latent constructs in a similar manner. In other words, the factor structure holds across groups, supporting the hypothesis that the conceptualization of energy capabilities is broadly shared between the two regions.

Metric model: Testing Whether Items Behave the Same Way

Constraining the factor loadings to be equal across regions leads to a significant deterioration in model fit, as indicated by the comparison between the configural and metric models ($\Delta\chi^2 = 487.54$, $\Delta df = 17$, $p < .001$, RMSEA = 0.043). This result suggests that metric invariance is not supported, implying that at least some items relate to the underlying constructs differently across regions.

Scalar model: Testing Whether Response Levels Are Comparable

Adding constraints on intercepts results in a substantial worsening of model fit, as shown by the comparison between the metric and scalar models ($\Delta\chi^2 = 4572.3$, $\Delta df = 17$, $p < .001$, RMSEA = 0.134). The sharp increase in RMSEA and the highly significant chi-square difference indicate a clear violation of scalar invariance. This means that mean differences in item responses cannot be interpreted without bias across regions. The lack of scalar invariance further indicates that direct comparisons of latent means between the Global North and South are not meaningful unless partial invariance can be achieved.

To explore the sources of scalar non-invariance, we examined the modification indices (MIs) from the scalar model. These indices estimate the extent to which model fit would improve if specific constraints, such as equal intercepts or loadings across groups, were relaxed. High MIs point to parameters that likely differ significantly between the Global North and Global South, indicating potential sources of misfit in the scalar model.

The highest modification indices in the scalar invariance model point to specific items that likely contributed to the violation of scalar invariance. In particular, items C8_Renewables, C6_WasteAvoidance, and C6_PolicyCompetence consistently show large modification indices across multiple factors, indicating substantial differences in their intercepts between the Global North and South. These discrepancies suggest that respondents from the two regions may interpret or respond to these items in systematically different ways.

Partial Scalar Invariance: Finding Problematic Items and Fixing the Model for Fair Comparisons

Based on these results, relaxing the intercept constraints for these items is justified in order to test for partial scalar invariance. This strategy enables meaningful cross-regional comparisons of latent means while accounting for limited measurement non-invariance. The intercept constraints for these items were therefore relaxed, resulting in a partial scalar invariance model. This approach enables valid comparisons of latent means while accommodating a limited number of cross-group item-level differences. The partial scalar model demonstrated improved fit statistics (CFI = 0.931, RMSEA = 0.052, and SRMR = 0.049) indicating that this level of invariance is acceptable for comparing latent means across the two groups. The final model, therefore, achieves partial scalar invariance by freeing intercept constraints on three non-invariant items, allowing for meaningful comparisons of latent means between the Global North and Global South while preserving an acceptable level of measurement equivalence. These results support the overall validity of the scale across regions, with only minor adjustments required.

4.3 Content Validity: Associations with Relative Deprivation

To assess whether people's energy-related opportunities align with their overall sense of fairness in life, we calculate polyserial correlations between the six capability factors and Callan et al.'s (2011) Personal Relative Deprivation Scale (PRDS). Relative deprivation is a well-established psychological precursor of perceiving injustice compared to one's peers, so these correlations offer a meaningful test of whether the EN-CAP factors reflect broader justice experiences or instead capture a more domain-specific form of energy-related constraint.

The correlations reveal a clear hierarchy of associations with relative deprivation (see Table 6). Adequate household energy supply (Factor 3) shows the strongest negative correlation with deprivation, indicating that lacking sufficient, reliable, and safe energy is most closely tied to feeling worse off in life. Energy-related health impacts (Factor 4) also correlate distinctly with deprivation, underscoring the central role of energy for basic wellbeing. Moderate associations emerge for informed decision-making, energy-related barriers to daily life, and rational and eco-friendly energy use (Factors 1, 2 and 5), suggesting that reduced knowledge, emotional strain, or limited agency in managing energy use likewise align with higher perceived

deprivation. By contrast, participation and representation in energy policy (Factor 6) shows no meaningful correlation with deprivation, implying that feeling unheard by policymakers is widespread but not interpreted as a personal status disadvantage.

The effect sizes for factors 3 and 4 fall within the “medium” range by the standards of psychological research (Funder & Ozer, 2019); thus they are substantively meaningful: the EN-CAP Scale targets a single life domain, yet it nonetheless displays systematic connections to general perceptions of justice and unfairness. Together, these findings demonstrate that lower energy capabilities are associated with a higher tendency to feel deprived, reinforcing the interpretation that the EN-CAP Scale captures a meaningful dimension of energy justice that resonates with individuals’ broader lived experience.

Table 6: Correlation between factors and PRDS

PRDS Index	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6
1.000	-0.143	-0.154	-0.243	-0.203	-0.182	0.014

Source: authors’ elaboration

5. Discussion: From an Ideal to a Measurable Experience

The findings of this study provide a robust theoretical and empirical foundation for understanding how energy systems influence human well-being. The study developed and validated the EN-CAP Scale (for the complete final scale, see Table 7), a comprehensive instrument capturing the social implications of energy systems through the lens of the CA. Factor analysis revealed a coherent six-factor structure representing distinct, yet interconnected, energy-related capabilities. While the capability Life is not included in the final scale, we argue, its core aspects are partially captured by the Bodily Health items, allowing the structure to maintain the conceptual rigor of Sen and Nussbaum’s CA and remain relevant for contemporary energy justice research.

The results indicate that energy well-being extends beyond mere access or affordability. Instead, it encompasses a multidimensional set of freedoms and effective opportunities, reflecting what people are actually able to do and be in their lives. The six-factor model provides a statistically robust framework to analyze how energy systems enable or constrain substantive freedoms. High overall model fit (CFI = .950, TLI = .941, RMSEA = .047, SRMR = .043) and consistent reliability across dimensions confirm that the instrument reliably captures energy-related capabilities across diverse contexts. Crucially, the model operationalizes the normative foundations of agency, dignity, and justice quantitatively without compromising conceptual integrity.

Table 6: Validated EN-CAP Scale – Dimensions, Core Meanings, and Corresponding Indicators

Dimension	Core Meaning	Indicators
Factor 1: Rational and Eco-Friendly Energy Use	This factor reflects a person’s ability to make deliberate, value-based choices about their energy	- C6_EnergyManagement: Are you able to optimize and manage your energy consumption in the most efficient way possible? - C6_PolicyCompetence: Do you feel competent about

	<p>use and their capacity to act in an environmentally responsible way. It combines practical reasoning about energy with ecological consciousness.</p> <p>Capabilities represented: Practical Reason and Other Species</p>	<p>energy policies and regulations that may impact your energy choices?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C6_WasteAvoidance: Are you able to avoid unnecessary waste of energy in your household? - C8_EcoAction: Are you able to engage in environmental and climate protection? - C8_Renewables: Are you able to choose to use renewable energy sources (for cooking, heating, vehicle's fuel, etc.)? - C8_EcoPurchasing: Are you able to choose environmentally friendly alternatives when you make purchasing decisions?
Factor 2: Energy-Related Barriers to Daily Life	<p>This factor captures the way energy affects emotional wellbeing and leisure. It reflects whether energy constraints create stress, limit social life, or diminish opportunities for enjoyment and recreation.</p> <p>Capabilities represented: Emotions and Play</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C5_StudyWork: Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to study or work at home? - C5_Hosting: Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to have visitors at your home? - C5_HomeSecurity: Does affordability or availability of energy impact your sense of safety and security in your home? - C9_DigitalAccess: Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to access online and digital communication services such as websites, messaging, and phone calls? - C9_Recreation: Does affordability or availability of energy impact your ability to enjoy recreational activities (such as TV, radio, and music) and hobbies in your home?
Factor 3: Adequate Household Energy Supply	<p>This factor reflects whether households have sufficient and reliable energy to support secure living and unrestricted mobility.</p> <p>Capabilities represented: Affiliation and Bodily Integrity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C7_Affordability: I can financially afford the amount of energy and energy resources required to supply all areas of my household. - C7_Availability: Energy and energy resources are available to me in the amounts needed to supply my household. - C7_Reliability: My household's energy and energy resources supply are reliable without outages. - C7_Safety: The energy use in my household does not cause any harm or risks to my health (including the sourcing of materials and energy generation). - C3_SafeMobility: Are you able to move from one place to another without fear of energy-related hazards (such as electrical shocks, gas leaks, fires caused by faulty wiring, and other similar dangers)?
Factor 4: Energy-Related Health Impacts	<p>This factor represents energy's role in supporting basic survival and health.</p> <p>Capabilities represented: Bodily Health</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C2_Health: Is your health impacted by affordability or availability of your energy use? - C2_LocalEnergyEffects: Is your health impacted by the energy situation in your area?
Factor 5: Energy Knowledge and Informed Decision-Making	<p>This factor captures the cognitive and informational capabilities related to understanding energy, making informed decisions, and aligning energy use with personal values.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - C4_InformedDecision: Are you able to make informed decisions about your energy use? - C4_EnergyOpinion: Are you able to form an opinion about energy issues such as energy sources available and how energy is produced or distributed? - C4_ConsciousEnergyUse: Are you able to make conscious choices about your energy use in line with your values?

	Capabilities represented: Senses, Imagination & Thought	
Factor 6: Participation and Representation in Energy Policy	This factor represents people's political empowerment and ability to influence or participate in decision-making related to energy.	- C10_PoliticiansContact: Politicians strive to keep in close touch with the people regarding energy issues. - C10_PoliticiansCare: Politicians care about what ordinary people think about energy issues.
	Capabilities represented: Control Over One's Environment (political participation domain)	

Source: authors' elaboration

This multidimensional framework links directly to the three core tenets of energy justice: distributive, procedural, and recognition justice (Sovacool & Dworkin, 2015):

- 1) Distributive justice concerns the fair allocation of resources and risks. Through the CA, it is understood in terms of equitable opportunities and capabilities: energy should enable people to live safely, work, study, and participate in everyday life, rather than merely providing access to kilowatt-hours;
- 2) Justice in recognition involves acknowledging diverse values, needs, and life plans. The CA operationalizes this through value-concordant functioning, ensuring that individuals can make choices consistent with their preferences, cultural context, and environmental responsibilities - for example, the ability to adopt sustainable energy practices without discrimination or constraint;
- 3) Procedural justice emphasizes participation and influence in decision-making. The CA captures this through agency, operationalized in this study via perceived political responsiveness, reflecting the extent to which individuals can shape energy policy and decisions affecting their well-being.

Together, these dimensions transform energy justice from an ethical ideal into a measurable structure of human capabilities, bridging normative theory and empirical research. The factor analysis further revealed nuanced patterns of how capabilities are experienced in practice. Some theoretically distinct capabilities cluster empirically, reflecting intertwined lived experiences: Practical Reason and Concern for other Species, for instance, align closely: energy competence and ecological agency seem to reinforce one another, suggesting that reflective engagement with energy issues is inseparable from having real opportunities to act sustainably. Likewise, Emotions and Play form a coherent cluster, indicating that emotional well-being and leisure are jointly shaped by access to energy, which provides comfort, security, and the means for recreational and social participation. A third cluster combines Affiliation and Bodily Integrity, showing that secure and affordable energy is fundamental to physical safety, mobility, and protection from energy-related hazards. These clusters underscore that energy capabilities are not experienced in isolation but as interconnected aspects of daily life. They also illuminate the

“missing middle” in existing energy indicators - the lived, social, and embodied consequences of energy systems that are often overlooked in purely technical or economic metrics.

Building on both the EFA and CFA, the multi-group assessment adds another layer by showing that cross-regional comparison is possible yet still requires careful handling of contextual variation. Configural invariance was achieved with excellent fit, showing that respondents in the Global North and South conceptualize the six underlying constructs in similar ways. However, full metric and scalar invariance did not hold initially, indicating that some items function differently across regions. By freeing the intercepts of three items related to renewable energy choice, competence in energy policies, and avoidance of energy waste, the model reached partial scalar invariance, an acceptable standard for comparing latent means between groups (Milfont & Fischer 2010; Putnick & Bornstein 2016). These deviations are theoretically informative: they point to the ways in which contextual realities, such as market access, infrastructural limitations, and policy environments, may affect how individuals interpret and respond to certain items. This also confirms previous literature highlighting how there are contextual and cultural structural differences in the way in which individuals tend to answer survey items (Chen et al., 1995; Heine et al., 2002; Van de Vijver & Tanzer, 2004).

Eventually, the scale offers concrete policy relevance. The six identified dimensions allow energy justice to be conceptualized as a continuum of opportunities and vulnerabilities, offering an empirical foundation for more context-sensitive and targeted policy design. Integrating capability indicators into ex-ante policy evaluations would make it possible to assess whether energy interventions genuinely expand people’s substantive freedoms, rather than merely providing technical or economic access. The scale can also deepen understandings of socio-energy barriers and the intersections between energy, gender, and human development. Each factor can serve as an indicator within a “capability dashboard” designed to assess the justice dimensions of energy transitions. This instrument can complement conventional indicators, such as energy burden or outage frequency, by illuminating the human implications of policy and infrastructural change. For example, electrification programs and renewable deployments can be assessed in terms of whether they expand people’s opportunities to work, study, and communicate, rather than merely increasing access to kilowatt-hours.

Limitations and Future Research

Nevertheless, some limitations must be acknowledged. First, the use of online panel surveys excludes segments of the population with limited or no internet access, precisely those most likely to experience severe forms of energy deprivation. Although demographic weighting and data quality controls mitigate bias, future studies should complement this approach with mixed-mode designs or targeted outreach to underrepresented groups. Second, residual correlations between closely worded items, as well as localized cross-loadings, indicate areas for refinement to improve conceptual clarity and reduce redundancy. Third, in the final scale, the Life capability was not retained. Initially measured with a single item (C1_Pollution), it was excluded during the EFA due to the lack of significant factor loading. Notably, the items assessing Bodily Health closely overlapped with Life, thereby partly compensating for its omission. Nevertheless, future research could address this by developing more distinct and nuanced items for Life, ensuring that each capability is captured independently and

comprehensively. Fourth, longitudinal and mixed-method approaches could further assess whether changes in energy policy or access conditions translate into measurable variations in capability scores, capturing the dynamic evolution of substantive freedoms over time. Last, responses to survey questions about energy issues are inherently subjective, raising concerns about the reliability and precision of consensual indicators. Differences in how households interpret their capabilities make these measures difficult to standardize. At the same time, however, subjective assessments may better capture the lived experiences and real consequences of the complex, interconnected factors driving energy vulnerability (Herrero, 2017). In light of this, employing a multiple-indicator approach - combining our capability-based instrument with objective measurements – may provide a robust approach for addressing these complexities.

Future research could build on this work by applying the instrument across a wider range of socio-economic and geographic contexts to deepen the understanding of how energy systems shape people’s lived experiences. In particular, integrating the measure into large-scale surveys on energy injustices or energy poverty would offer valuable insights into how unequal access to energy resources and services translates into capability constraints. Such applications would also allow researchers to investigate the structural and contextual conditions under which specific capabilities are strengthened or undermined. Moreover, analyzing the relationships among the different capabilities themselves, for example, how constraints in one domain may reinforce or mitigate limitations in others, could yield deeper insights into the complex, multidimensional nature of energy-related wellbeing.

6. Conclusion

A comprehensive measurement of energy-related well-being is essential for understanding the multidimensional nature of energy justice. Our factor analysis of the EN-CAP Scale identified six distinct factors, each capturing a unique constellation of energy capabilities and revealing how participants perceive and prioritize different aspects of energy justice in their daily lives. The full set of 23 items - with the exception of the capability Life - remained in their original configuration within their designated energy capabilities, ensuring that the instrument’s theoretical framework was fully preserved.

Overall, this study advances both the conceptual and empirical dialogue between energy justice and the CA. Conceptually, it advances a framework in which energy systems are understood not only as infrastructures for supply but as infrastructures of opportunity, shaping what people can be and do. Empirically, it demonstrates that these opportunities can be measured, compared, and tracked across countries in a rigorous and statistically defensible manner. Practically, it provides a tool for policymakers, researchers, and advocates to assess the justice dimensions of energy transitions in ways that reflect the complexity of lived experience rather than abstract economic proxies. By grounding energy research in the language of capabilities, the study shifts the analytical focus from what energy systems deliver to what people are actually able to achieve through them, which is an essential step toward designing transitions that are equitable, inclusive, and genuinely transformative.

To our knowledge, this study is the first attempt to develop and quantitatively validate a CA-based scale for measuring energy well-being on a multinational sample exceeding 30,000 respondents. The combination of exploratory, confirmatory, and multigroup factor analysis represents a significant step toward building comparable and culturally sensitive instruments. The achievement of partial scalar invariance confirms the stability of the scale for cross-regional comparisons while preserving flexibility across diverse socio-economic and cultural contexts. Taken together, our instrument offers a solid foundation for comprehensively measuring the societal impacts of energy and informing policy interventions designed to understand and address energy justice.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme *Culture, creativity and inclusive society* under grant agreement no. 101094326. We gratefully acknowledge Ipsos for coordinating and conducting the cross-national survey fieldwork. We also thank Professor Rosie Day (University of Birmingham) for her valuable intellectual exchange and support throughout the development of the capabilities. Finally, we are sincerely grateful to all survey respondents for their time and participation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to provide targeted assistance with tasks including content organization, writing and formatting R code, as well as proofreading and improving the clarity and readability of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as necessary and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

References

- Azmoodeh, M., Haghghi, F., & Motieyan, H. (2023). The capability approach and social equity in transport: Understanding factors affecting capabilities of urban residents, using structural equation modeling. *Transport Policy*, *142*, 137–151.
- Baker, E., Carley, S., Castellanos, S., Nock, D., Bozeman III, J. F., Konisky, D., ... & Sovacool, B. (2023). Metrics for decision-making in energy justice. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, *48*(1), 737–760.
- Baltruszewicz, M., Steinberger, J. K., Paavola, J., Ivanova, D., Brand-Correa, L. I., & Owen, A. (2023). Social outcomes of energy use in the United Kingdom: Household energy footprints and their links to well-being. *Ecological Economics*, *205*, 107686.
- Bartiaux, F., Vandeschrick, C., Moezzi, M., & Frogneux, N. (2018). Energy justice, unequal access to affordable warmth, and capability deprivation: A quantitative analysis for Belgium. *Applied Energy*, *225*, 1219–1233.
- Bartiaux, F., Day, R., & Lahaye, W. (2021). Energy poverty as a restriction of multiple capabilities: A systemic approach for Belgium. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, *22*, 270–291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2021.1887107>
- Bartolomei, L., Blundo-Canto, G., & De Muro, P. (2024). How is the capability approach applied to assess well-being impacts? A systematic review. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, *25*(3), 367–399.
- Bell, S. E., Daggett, C., & Labuski, C. (2020). Toward feminist energy systems: Why adding women and solar panels is not enough☆. *Energy research & social science*, *68*, 101557.
- Bouzarovski, S. (2014). Energy poverty in the European Union: Landscapes of vulnerability. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Energy and Environment*, *3*(3), 276–289.
- Bouzarovski, S., & Petrova, S. (2015). A global perspective on domestic energy deprivation: Overcoming the energy poverty–fuel poverty binary. *Energy Research & Social Science*, *10*, 31–40.
- Brand-Correa, L. I., & Steinberger, J. K. (2017). A framework for decoupling human need satisfaction from energy use. *Ecological Economics*, *141*, 43–52.
- Brown, T. A. (2006). *Confirmatory factor analysis for applied research* (1st ed.). Guilford Publications.
- Byrne, B. M., Shavelson, R. J., & Muthén, B. (1989). Testing for the equivalence of factor covariance and mean structures: The issue of partial measurement invariance. *Psychological Bulletin*, *105*(3), 456.
- Cantoni, R., Caprotti, F., & de Groot, J. (2022). Solar energy at the peri-urban frontier: An energy justice study of urban peripheries from Burkina Faso and South Africa. *Energy Research & Social Science*, *94*, 102884.

- Callan, M. J., Shead, N. W., & Olson, J. M. (2011). *Personal relative deprivation, delay discounting, and gambling*. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 101(5), 955–973. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0024778>
- Cao, M., & Hickman, R. (2019). Understanding travel and differential capabilities and functionings in Beijing. *Transport Policy*, 83, 46–56.
- Cao, M., & Hickman, R. (2020). Transport, social equity and capabilities in East Beijing. In *Handbook on transport and urban transformation in China* (pp. 317–332). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Chen, C., Shin-ying, L., & Stevenson, H. W. (1995). Response style and cross-cultural comparisons of rating scales among East Asian and North American students. *Psychological Science*, 6, 170–175.
- David, D., & Kod'ousková, H. (2023). Official narratives vs. lived experiences: Contrasting views on energy poverty in the Czech Republic. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 97, 102991.
- Day, R., Burchell, K., & Thomson, H. (2023). Questionnaire for the Community Energy for Energy Solidarity project [Unpublished questionnaire].
- Day, R., Walker, G., & Simcock, N. (2016). Conceptualising energy use and energy poverty using a capabilities framework. *Energy Policy*, 93, 255–264.
- DeVellis, R. F., & Thorpe, C. T. (2021). *Scale development: Theory and applications*. Sage publications.
- Devine-Wright, P. (2005). Beyond NIMBYism: Towards an integrated framework for understanding public perceptions of wind energy. *Wind Energy: An International Journal for Progress and Applications in Wind Power Conversion Technology*, 8(2), 125–139.
- Dunlap, A., & Tornel, C. (2023). Pluralizing energy justice? Towards cultivating an unruly, autonomous and insurrectionary research agenda. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 103, 103217.
- Ellis, G., Schneider, N., & Wüstenhagen, R. (2023). Dynamics of social acceptance of renewable energy: An introduction to the concept. *Energy Policy*, 181, 113706.
- European Commission. (2022a). Energy poverty in the EU. European Commission. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/markets-and-consumers/energy-consumer-rights/energy-poverty_en
- European Commission. (2022b). EU energy poverty advisory hub. European Commission. https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/index_en
- Fabrigar, L. R., & Wegener, D. T. (2012). *Exploratory factor analysis*. Oxford University Press.
- Farmer, A. Y., & Lawrence Farmer, G. (2014). *Research with diverse groups: Research designs and multivariate latent modeling for equivalence*. Oxford University Press.

- Ferrall-Wolf, I., Gill-Wiehl, A., & Kammen, D. M. (2023). A bibliometric review of energy justice literature. *Frontiers in Sustainable Energy Policy*, 2, 1175736. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsuep.2023.1175736>
- Funder, D. C., & Ozer, D. J. (2019). Evaluating effect size in psychological research: Sense and nonsense. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 2(2), 156–168. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245919847202>
- Galvin, R., & Sunikka-Blank, M. (2018). Economic inequality and household energy consumption in high-income countries: A challenge for social science based energy research. *Ecological Economics*, 153, 78–88.
- Gore, T. (2020). Confronting carbon inequality: Putting climate justice at the heart of the COVID-19 recovery.
- Guevara, Z., Mendoza-Tinoco, D., & Silva, D. (2023). The theoretical peculiarities of energy poverty research: A systematic literature review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 105, 103274.
- Gupta, J., Liverman, D., Prodani, K., Aldunce, P., Bai, X., Broadgate, W., ... & Verburg, P. H. (2023). Earth system justice needed to identify and live within Earth system boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 6(6), 630-638.
- Groskurth, K., Nießen, D., Rammstedt, B., & Lechner, C. M. (2021). An English-language adaptation and validation of the Political Efficacy Short Scale (PESS). *Measurement Instruments for the Social Sciences*, 3(1), 1.
- Hall, S. M., Hards, S., & Bulkeley, H. (2013). New approaches to energy: Equity, justice and vulnerability. Introduction to the special issue. *Local Environment*, 18(4), 413–421.
- Harrington, D. (2009). *Confirmatory factor analysis*. Oxford university press.
- Heffron, R. J., & McCauley, D. (2017). The concept of energy justice across the disciplines. *Energy Policy*, 105, 658–667.
- Heine, S. J., Lehman, D. R., Peng, K., & Greenholtz, J. (2002). What's wrong with cross-cultural comparisons of subjective Likert scales?: The reference-group effect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 82(6), 903.
- Herrero, S. T. (2017). Energy poverty indicators: A critical review of methods. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 26(7), 1018–1031.
- Hickman, R., Cao, M., Lira, B. M., Fillone, A., & Biona, J. B. (2017). Understanding capabilities, functionings and travel in high and low income neighbourhoods in Manila. *Social Inclusion*, 5(4), 161-174.
- Hillerbrand, R., & Goldammer, K. (2018). Energy technologies and human well-being: Using sustainable design for the energy transition. In *The Future of Engineering: Philosophical Foundations, Ethical Problems and Application Cases* (pp. 151–175). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

- Hillerbrand, R., Milchram, C., & Schippl, J. (2021). Using the capability approach as a normative perspective on energy justice: Insights from two case studies on digitalisation in the energy sector. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 22(2), 336–359.
- Hihetah, C., Gallachóir, B. Ó., Dunphy, N. P., & Harris, C. (2024). A systematic review of the lived experiences of the energy vulnerable: Where are the research gaps? *Energy Research & Social Science*, 114, 103565.
- Horn, J. L. (1965). A rationale and test for the number of factors in factor analysis. *Psychometrika*, 30(2), 179–185.
- Jenkins, K., McCauley, D., Heffron, R., Stephan, H., & Rehner, R. (2016). Energy justice: A conceptual review. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 11, 174–182.
- Kalt, G., Wiedenhofer, D., Görg, C., & Haberl, H. (2019). Conceptualizing energy services: A review of energy and well-being along the Energy Service Cascade. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 53, 47–58.
- Kaiser, H. F. (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *psychometrika*, 39(1), 31-36.
- Liao, C., Erbaugh, J. T., Kelly, A. C., & Agrawal, A. (2021). Clean energy transitions and human well-being outcomes in lower and middle income countries: A systematic review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 145, 111063.
- Lorgelly, P. K., Lorimer, K., Fenwick, E. A., Briggs, A. H., & Anand, P. (2015). Operationalising the capability approach as an outcome measure in public health: The development of the OCAP-18. *Social Science & Medicine*, 142, 68–81.
- Melin, A., Day, R., & Jenkins, K. E. (2021). Energy justice and the capability approach—Introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 22(2), 185–196.
- Menyhárt, B. (2024). Energy poverty in the European Union: The art of kaleidoscopic measurement. *Energy Policy*, 190, 114160.
- Middlemiss, L., & Gillard, R. (2015). Fuel poverty from the bottom-up: Characterising household energy vulnerability through the lived experience of the fuel poor. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 6, 146-154.
- Milfont, T. L., & Fischer, R. (2010). Testing measurement invariance across groups: Applications in cross-cultural research. *International Journal of Psychological Research*, 3(1), 111–130.
- Moniruzzaman, M., & Day, R. (2020). Gendered energy poverty and energy justice in rural Bangladesh. *Energy Policy*, 144, 111554.
- Nussbaum, M. C. (2000a). *Women and human development: The capabilities approach* (Vol. 3). Cambridge University Press.
- Nussbaum, M. (2000b). Women's capabilities and social justice. *Journal of Human Development*, 1(2), 219–247.

- Nussbaum, M. (2003). Capabilities as fundamental entitlements: Sen and social justice. *Feminist Economics*, 9(2–3), 33–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1354570022000077926>
- Putnick, D. L., & Bornstein, M. H. (2016). Measurement invariance conventions and reporting: The state of the art and future directions for psychological research. *Developmental Review*, 41, 71–90.
- Qazi, A., Hussain, F., Rahim, N. A., Hardaker, G., Alghazzawi, D., Shaban, K., & Haruna, K. (2019). Towards sustainable energy: A systematic review of renewable energy sources, technologies, and public opinions. *IEEE Access*, 7, 63837–63851.
- Rao, N. D., & Wilson, C. (2022). Advancing energy and well-being research. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(2), 98–103.
- Ren, W., Guan, Y., Qiu, F., Levin, T., & Heleno, M. (2025). Energy justice and equity: A review of definitions, measures, and practice in policy, planning, and operations. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 222, 115900.
- Rubin, D. B. (1987). Multiple imputation for survey nonresponse.
- Schafer, J. L., & Graham, J. W. (2002). Missing data: our view of the state of the art. *Psychological methods*, 7(2), 147.
- Sen, A. (1992). Inequality reexamined. *Oxford University Press*.
- Sen, A. (1999). Commodities and capabilities. *OUP Catalogue*.
- Sen, A. (2014). Development as freedom. In G. R. Gupta & M. T. R. (Eds.), *The globalization and development reader: Perspectives on development and global change* (pp. 525).
- Snell, C., Bevan, M., & Thomson, H. (2015). Justice, fuel poverty and disabled people in England. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 10, 123–132.
- Sovacool, B. K., & Dworkin, M. H. (2015). Energy justice: Conceptual insights and practical applications. *Applied Energy*, 142, 435–444.
- Sovacool, B. K., Lipson, M. M., & Chard, R. (2019). Temporality, vulnerability, and energy justice in household low carbon innovations. *Energy policy*, 128, 495–504.
- Sovacool, B. K., Bell, S. E., Daggett, C., Labuski, C., Lennon, M., Naylor, L., ... & Firestone, J. (2023). Pluralizing energy justice: Incorporating feminist, anti-racist, Indigenous, and postcolonial perspectives. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 97, 102996.
- Sovacool, B. K., Dunlap, A. A., & Novaković, B. (2025). When decarbonization reinforces colonization: Complex energy injustice and solar energy development in the California desert. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 115(3), 640–670.
- Sy, S. A., & Mokaddem, L. (2022). Energy poverty in developing countries: A review of the concept and its measurements. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 89, 102562.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Experimental designs using ANOVA* (Vol. 724). Thomson/Brooks/Cole.

Thomson, H., Bouzarovski, S., & Snell, C. (2017a). Rethinking the measurement of energy poverty in Europe: A critical analysis of indicators and data. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 26(7), 879–901.

Thomson, H., Snell, C., & Bouzarovski, S. (2017b). Health, well-being and energy poverty in Europe: A comparative study of 32 European countries. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(6), 584.

Van de Vijver & Tanzer 2004

Velasco-Herrejon, P., & Bauwens, T. (2020). Energy justice from the bottom up: A capability approach to community acceptance of wind energy in Mexico. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 70, 101711.

Wiedmann, T., Lenzen, M., Keyßer, L. T., & Steinberger, J. K. (2020). Scientists' warning on affluence. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 3107.

Willand, N., Middha, B., & Walker, G. (2021). Using the capability approach to evaluate energy vulnerability policies and initiatives in Victoria, Australia. *Local Environment*, 26(9), 1109–1127.

Wüstenhagen, R., Wolsink, M., & Bürer, M. J. (2007). Social acceptance of renewable energy innovation: An introduction to the concept. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2683–2691.

Zwick, W. R., & Velicer, W. F. (1986). Comparison of five rules for determining the number of components to retain. *Psychological Bulletin*, 99(3), 432–442.

<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.99.3.432>